

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center

Milestone 2 Target Enabling Package

NLRP3 (NLR family pyrin domain containing 3)

Gene Symbol/Name	NLRP3 (NLR family pyrin domain containing 3)
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Ensembl ID	ENSG00000162711
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1. ABSTRACT

The TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) centers were established to provide high-quality research tools and technologies to validate and advance the next generation of drug targets for Alzheimer's disease (AD). Data, methods, and experimental resources are being openly disseminated to the AD research community to accelerate target discovery and validation. These resources are compiled as Target Enablement Packages (TEPs) and made available through the AD Knowledge Portal. Here, the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center presents a Milestone 2 (M2) TEP that evaluates the experimental feasibility of initiating a drug discovery program targeting NLRP3 by establishing and assessing initial *in vitro* assays and tool molecules.

NLRP3 is a key sensor protein of the NLRP3 inflammasome complex that regulates caspase-1 activation and the maturation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and IL-18. NLRP3 activation in microglia has been implicated in driving chronic neuroinflammation, amyloid pathology, and tau aggregation in AD. To experimentally validate literature-reported NLRP3 inhibitors and benchmark assay performance, we established paired high-content imaging assays that quantitatively measure ASC speck formation and pyroptosis in THP-1 cell models. Using these assays, we evaluated a panel of small molecules reported to directly bind the NLRP3 NACHT domain, including MCC950, Inzomelid, and two structurally distinct fused bicyclic heteroaryl chemotypes selected from a recently disclosed patent based on their potency and CNS drug-like properties. The results reproduced literature-reported activities and identified previously unreported racemic analogs of the patent selected compounds with low-nanomolar potency. Together, these findings validate our cell-based assay platform for quantitative evaluation of NLRP3 inhibitors and provide the research community with reference compounds, data, and methods to enable further investigation of NLRP3 as a therapeutic target in AD.

2. BACKGROUND

NLRP3 (Nucleotide-binding domain, Leucine-rich repeat-containing family, Pyrin domain-containing 3; also known as NOD-like receptor family pyrin domain-containing 3 and officially named NLR family pyrin domain containing 3) is a protein encoded by the NLRP3 gene in humans.¹ It is a member of the NOD-like receptor (NLR) family of proteins, which regulate the innate immune system. NOD-like receptors are intracellular pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) that recognize pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs), distinct from membrane-bound Toll-like receptors (TLRs) and C-type lectins (CTLs) that survey the extracellular milieu and endosomal compartments for PAMPs.² NLRP3 is particularly known for its role in forming the NLRP3 inflammasome, a multiprotein complex that plays a critical role in inflammation and the immune response. The NLRP3 inflammasome serves as a molecular platform that activates caspase-1, an enzyme responsible for the maturation and secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and interleukin-18 (IL-18). Activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome can be triggered by various danger signals, including PAMPs and damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs).³ These signals, released during cellular stress, injury, or infection, are sensed by NLRP3, leading to inflammasome assembly and subsequent immune activation.³

Figure 1. Structural organization of the NLRP3 inflammasome. (A) Schematic representation of the canonical NLRP3/AIM2 inflammasome complex, comprising a sensor molecule (NLRP3/AIM2), adaptor protein (ASC), and effector molecule (pro-caspase-1). Upon activation, NLRP3 undergoes ATP-dependent oligomerization via the NACHT domain and recruits NEK7 to form the active inflammasome complex through PYD-PYD and CARD-CARD interactions. (B) Cryo-EM structure of the NLRP3-NEK7 complex (PDB ID: 6NPY) shown in two orientations (180° rotation). Major domains including the LRR (leucine-rich repeat), NACHT (comprising HD1, WHD, NBD, and HD2), and the associated NEK7 are annotated (PYD is not included in the Cryo-EM structure). A linear domain map of NLRP3 is included at the bottom for reference.

Several inflammasomes that activate caspase-1, as mentioned above, have been fully characterized and are named after the NLR or AIM2-like receptor (ALR) protein scaffolds that form their core structures, with the NLRP3 inflammasome being the most extensively studied.⁴ The inflammasome structure (as exemplified by NLRP3 and AIM2) generally consists of three components: a sensor molecule, an adaptor protein, and an effector molecule (**Figure 1A**). The sensor molecule is typically a cytosolic pattern recognition receptor (PRR), as previously described, and belongs either to the NLR family (e.g., NLRP1, NLRP3, or NLRC4) or to the ALR family (e.g., AIM2). The adaptor protein bridges the sensor and effector molecules through protein-protein interactions (PPIs). In the NLRP3 inflammasome, the adaptor protein is the apoptosis-associated speck-like protein containing a CARD (ASC), which connects the NLRP3 sensor to the pro-caspase-1 effector via PYD-PYD and CARD-CARD interactions respectively. In some inflammasomes, such as NLRP1, the adaptor protein is absent, and the sensor molecule (NLRP1) is capable of directly interacting with pro-caspase-1. The effector molecule, pro-caspase-1, interacts with ASC via its CARD domain and, upon activation and autoproteolysis, cleaves the precursor cytokines IL-1 β and IL-18 into their mature forms. The detailed structure of the NLRP3 sensor molecule and the structural basis for its oligomerization, which facilitates NLRP3 inflammasome activation, have been extensively studied using cryo-EM.⁵ As shown in **Figure 1B**, the cytosolic NLRP3 receptor consists of three main domains: an N-terminal pyrin domain (PYD), a central NACHT domain, and a C-terminal leucine-rich repeat (LRR) domain. The PYD domain mediates interactions with the adaptor protein ASC via PYD-PYD interactions. The central NACHT domain comprises multiple subdomains, including the nucleotide-binding domain (NBD), helical domain 1 (HD1), winged-helix domain (WHD), and helical domain 2 (HD2). The NBD is responsible for ATP binding and hydrolysis, which is a key mediator of NLRP3 inflammasome activation.

While the NLRP3 inflammasome plays a crucial role in host defense against pathogens and the maintenance of immune homeostasis, its dysregulation has been implicated in the development and progression of various inflammatory diseases, including autoinflammatory disorders, type 2 diabetes, atherosclerosis, and neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (AD), as extensively reviewed elsewhere.⁶ Owing to its central role in inflammation, the NLRP3 inflammasome has emerged as an important therapeutic target for the treatment of these conditions. In the early 2010s, a comprehensive review by Heneka and colleagues described the involvement of innate immune activation in the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative diseases, with a particular emphasis on AD.⁷ The authors summarized the literature up to 2014 and highlighted the pivotal role of NLRP3 inflammasome activation in microglia, which is triggered by misfolded host-derived proteins such as amyloid- β , leading to chronic neuroinflammation and neuronal dysfunction. In a subsequent study by the same research group, Venegas *et al.* provided direct experimental evidence linking NLRP3 inflammasome activation to amyloid pathology in AD.⁸ They demonstrated that ASC specks released by activated microglia via the NLRP3 inflammasome act as cross-seeding agents that accelerate amyloid- β aggregation and spreading in the brain. This work offers a mechanistic explanation for how innate immune activation can drive disease progression and reinforces the pathogenic role of NLRP3 inflammasome signaling in AD. Later, another study by Ising *et al.* demonstrated that NLRP3 inflammasome activation not only promotes amyloid pathology but also drives tau hyperphosphorylation and aggregation, thereby linking NLRP3 signaling to both hallmark pathologies of AD.⁹ This finding further supports the central role of microglial NLRP3 inflammasome activation in the progression of AD and highlights it as a promising therapeutic target.

Drug discovery programs targeting NLRP3 were originally focused on developing broad anti-inflammatory drugs for peripheral indications. As a result, small molecule inhibitors like MCC950 generally lack central nervous system (CNS) drug-like properties. Currently there is no FDA approved drug specifically targeting NLRP3. Therefore, as an initial step, we selected from the literature a set of compounds reported to directly bind the NLRP3 NACHT domain, based on their CNS drug-like characteristics and potent inhibition of IL-1 β production, and evaluated them using a pair of high-content imaging assays developed by our cellular pharmacology laboratory that quantify ASC speck formation for inflammasome activation and cellular pyroptosis, respectively. Herein, we report our findings as part of a publicly available TEP.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 NLRP3 Inflammasome Inhibition Strategies

The inhibition of the NLRP3 inflammasome is best exploited by targeting its widely accepted two-step activation mechanism, which involves two sequential signals.¹⁰ Unlike other PRRs, the basal level of NLRP3 in macrophages is low, and prior to activation, its cytoplasmic expression must be upregulated, a process known as the priming step, typically initiated by Toll-like receptor (TLR) agonists such as lipopolysaccharides (LPS). This signaling leads to the activation of nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B), resulting in the upregulation of NLRP3 and pro-IL-1 β expression. Therefore, one strategy for inhibiting the NLRP3 inflammasome is to target the priming step (indirect targeting) by blocking key signal transduction mediators involved in this process, such as IRAK4 and I κ B kinases (IKKs), which phosphorylate the inhibitor of NF- κ B (I κ B) (**Figure 2**). Following the priming step, canonical activation of NLRP3 occurs upon recognition of an NLRP3 activator, which serves as the second signal and can range from microbial PAMPs to sterile DAMPs.⁶ Among these activation signals, the efflux of intracellular K⁺ was the first event identified as a key step in the NLRP3 activation process, triggered by various stimuli such as bacterial toxins, extracellular ATP, and various particulates.¹¹ As shown in **Figure 2**, primed NLRP3 sensor molecules exist in an inactive, closed-cage form, as evidenced by extensive cryo-EM structural elucidation studies.⁵ This conformation is stabilized through PPIs mediated by LRR domains. The mitotic serine/threonine kinase NEK7 acts as a binding partner by interacting with the LRR domain of NLRP3, disrupting the oligomeric cage and stabilizing inactive NLRP3 dimers and monomers. Upon activation signaling, ATP binding and hydrolysis at the NACHT domain of NLRP3 induces a conformational change that shifts the protein into an open, active conformation. This active form subsequently undergoes inflammasome complex assembly through PPIs with other components of the inflammasome. Therefore, the second strategy for inhibiting NLRP3 inflammasome activation is to directly target the activation step, primarily through the use of small molecules that bind to the NACHT domain of NLRP3 and inhibit the ATPase activity and stabilize its closed-inactive conformation, thereby preventing the conformational change required for transition to the active-open state. Numerous small molecules that bind to the NACHT domain, such as MCC950, CY-09, tranilast, and parthenolide, have been reported in the literature, and a comprehensive review can be found elsewhere.⁶ In the current study, we aimed to evaluate a selected set of structurally diverse compounds that directly bind the NLRP3 NACHT domain using our in-house optimized assay, with the goal of investigating the inhibition of ASC speck formation beyond the

conventional criterion of IL-1 β production inhibition typically employed in NLRP3 inflammasome drug discovery campaigns.

Figure 2. Therapeutic strategies for targeting the NLRP3 inflammasome. (A) Indirect inhibition (left) via blockade of the priming step through suppression of IL1R1 or TLR-mediated NF- κ B signaling (e.g. IRAK inhibition and IKKs (not shown)), which reduces transcriptional upregulation of NLRP3. **(B)** Direct inhibition (right) of NLRP3 activation by targeting conformational dynamics. In the inactive state, NLRP3 forms closed oligomeric cage-like assemblies stabilized by LRR-LRR interactions. Activation involves NEK7 binding and ATP-dependent conformational change of the NACHT domain, leading to the open-active state. Small molecule inhibitors such as MCC950 act on the NACHT domain to stabilize the inactive conformation and inhibit the ATPase activity, preventing inflammasome assembly.

3.2 Compound Selection

MCC950, one of the most widely studied NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitors, was originally discovered through a phenotype-based drug discovery campaign conducted by Pfizer in 1998, during which a diarylsulfonylurea-containing hit compound, glyburide, was found to inhibit IL-1 β production in a blood-derived monocyte-based phenotypic assay.¹² Subsequent optimization led to the development of MCC950, which demonstrated nanomolar potency in inhibiting IL-1 β production (**Figure 3**).¹³

Figure 3. Phenotype-driven discovery and optimization of NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitor MCC950. Initial screening identified glyburide, a sulfonylurea antidiabetic, as a weak inhibitor of IL-1 β production (hit). SAR efforts led to the development of diarylsulfonylurea analogs CP-412 and CP-424 with improved potency. Further chemical optimization yielded MCC950 (also known as CRID3 or CP-456), a potent and selective inhibitor of NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Photoaffinity labeling studies revealed that MCC950 directly targets the NACHT domain of NLRP3, specifically binding to the ATP hydrolysis motif (NDB) and preventing conformational activation

Photoaffinity labeling experiments later confirmed that MCC950 directly binds to the NACHT domain of NLRP3.¹⁴ However, MCC950 suffers from poor brain penetration, limiting its utility to peripheral applications, and also exhibits hepatotoxicity and metabolic instability.¹⁵ These limitations prompted further optimization, ultimately yielding the MCC950-based diarylsulfonylurea clinical candidate GDC-2394.¹⁶ We carefully evaluated the structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies that led to GDC-2394 in terms of IL-1 β production inhibition potency and CNS drug-like properties, using a calculated CNS-MPO score.

A Central Nervous System–Multiparameter Optimization (CNS-MPO) score is an empirical metric used to evaluate the drug-like properties of a molecule, combining equally weighted physicochemical parameters (calculated octanol/water partition coefficient (cLogP/cLogD), molecular weight, total polar surface area (TPSA), hydrogen-bond donors, and pKa) into a score ranging from 0 to 6. A higher score predicts that a compound is more likely to have favorable drug-like properties and CNS exposure. By balancing multiple properties rather than using rigid cutoffs based on a single parameter, the CNS-MPO score defines CNS drug-like space, guides compound selection and design and ultimately reduces attrition in the clinical development of drugs for CNS indications.

We selected compounds containing the diarylsulfonylurea functionality that exhibits both potent IL-1 β inhibition and a higher CNS-MPO score. As shown in **Figure 4**, the most potent inhibitors identified are those with IL-1 β production inhibition IC₅₀ values below 30 nM, including MCC950 and the clinical candidate GDC-2394, which exhibited lower CNS-MPO scores, suggesting limited CNS drug-like properties. However, we were able to identify a subset of compounds (compounds **3-5**) with IL-1 β inhibition IC₅₀ values below 500 nM and CNS-MPO scores greater than 4. Among these, compound **5** is of particular interest, as it represents a structural isomer of Inzomelid (also known as Emlenoflast or MCC-7840; IZD-174) developed by the biotech company Inflazome (acquired by Roche). Inzomelid is diarylsulfonylurea-

containing NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitor with demonstrated brain exposure and potent IL-1 β inhibition (<100 nM IC₅₀).¹⁷ Based on this information, we included Inzomelid as one of the selected inhibitors that directly bind to NLRP3 with diarylsulfonylurea functionality. MCC950 was also included in this set of compounds to enable direct comparison.

Figure 4. Evaluation of MCC950-based NLRP3 inhibitors. A plot of CNS-MPO score vs pIC₅₀ values for these compounds highlights the trade-off between potency and CNS-relevant physicochemical properties. Compounds in the red-shaded region such as MCC950 and GDC-2394 (clinical candidate) are highly potent but exhibit suboptimal CNS MPO scores, whereas those in the green-shaded region (CNS-MPO > 4 and IC₅₀ < 500 nM) display a more favorable balance. Chemical structures and IL-1 β production inhibitory IC₅₀ values are shown for representative compounds. Two compounds selected for inclusion in the current study are depicted inside gray color boxes.

We also identified a set of NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitors with a novel chemotype that directly binds to the NLRP3 NACHT domain, distinct from the commonly encountered diarylsulfonylurea scaffold, exhibiting potent IL-1 β production inhibitory activity, as disclosed by Aitken *et al* (WO 2023/066825 A1).¹⁸ These compounds are characterized by the presence of a fused bicyclic heteroaryl moiety and a phenol functional group. We performed a similar analysis to identify a subset of compounds with potent IL-1 β production inhibitory activity and higher CNS-MPO scores using all the compounds that displayed <1.5 nM IC₅₀ in the pyroptosis assay. As shown in **Figure 5A**, we identified two synthetically accessible compounds (example 72A and 45) with pyroptosis IC₅₀ values below 1 nM and CNS-MPO scores greater than 3.5.

Example 72A possesses the absolute stereochemistry 3*a*S,7*a*R with a *cis* configuration, and following the protocol described for its synthesis, we prepared compounds **6a-d** corresponding to example 72A and its stereoisomers (**Figure 5B**). Compounds **6a** and **6b** represent two isomers with *cis* relative stereochemistry, obtained by chiral separation and denoted as *cis*-1 and *cis*-2, as the absolute stereochemistry was not assigned after chiral separation. However, as discussed later, based on the inflammasome inhibition IC₅₀ data, we concluded that compound **6a** is the analog with matching stereochemistry to example 72A. We also included the racemic version of example 72A (compound **6c**) and the analog with *trans* relative stereochemistry (compound **6d**). To evaluate the importance of the phenoxy functionality for NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitory activity, we synthesized the phenoxy methyl analogs of these compounds (compounds **7a-f**), and similarly, we prepared compound **8** corresponding to example 45 along with its phenoxy methyl analog **9**. We tested these compounds in a cellular assay specifically measuring inflammasome formation and pyroptosis to investigate their specific activity inhibiting inflammasome activation and a downstream pro-inflammatory form of programmed cell death.

Figure 5. Identification of NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitors for CNS applications. (A) CNS-MPO versus inhibitory potency of IL-1 β production (IC₅₀) analysis of a series of NLRP3 inhibitors derived from a chemotype distinct from MCC950. The chemical structures of two compounds (examples 72A and 45) selected for the current study are shown with their absolute stereochemistry. Compounds in the green-shaded area represent candidates with an optimal balance of potency and CNS drug-like properties (CNS-MPO > 3.5 and IC₅₀ < 1 nM). **(B)** Compounds **6a** and **6b** represent two isomers with *cis* relative stereochemistry, obtained by chiral separation and denoted as *cis*-1 and *cis*-2, as the absolute stereochemistry was not assigned in this experiment. Based on the inflammasome inhibition data (IC₅₀), we concluded that compound **6a** (highlighted in blue) is the analog with matching stereochemistry to example 72A. Compounds **6c** and **6d** are the racemic versions of example 72A with *cis* and *trans* relative stereochemistry, respectively. Compounds **7a-f** represent the phenoxy methylated versions. Compound **8** corresponds to example 45, and its phenoxy methylated analog is compound **9**.

3.3 Biological Evaluation

Our strategy for the characterization of NLRP3 inhibitors focused on 1) quantifying the inhibition of inflammasome formation in model cells and 2) quantifying key biological consequences mediated by the inflammasome in cells. For this purpose, we used the THP-1 cells, a well-validated cellular model for evaluating the pharmacology of drugs targeting NLRP3.¹⁹

The key biological characterization of NLRP3 inhibitors is to assess their ability to inhibit inflammasome formation. To this end, we established a cell-based model using THP-1/ASC-GFP stable cells (InvivoGen, cat:thp1-asc-gfp) by optimizing assay conditions based on literature reports (**Figure 6**).^{20,21} We found that significant inflammasome formation required cells in good health; when cell viability was below 90% in culture, the cells responded poorly to LPS-nigericin treatment and exhibited reduced inflammasome formation. Therefore, only cultures with viability above 95% were used to initiate assays.

Figure 6. General workflow of the optimized high-content imaging assays for NLRP3 inflammasome inhibition. THP-1 and THP1/ASC-GFP reporter cells were seeded at 10,000 cells per well in 384-well plates (Day 1), pretreated with test inhibitors (60 min) followed by LPS priming (10 ng/mL, 22 h; Day 2), and stimulated with nigericin (10 μ M, 90 min) to activate the NLRP3 inflammasome. Cells were then stained with Hoechst 33342 to visualize nuclei. ASC-GFP speck formation was quantified in THP1/ASC-GFP reporter cells or pyroptosis in wild-type THP-1 cells by Hoechst/propidium iodide dual staining. High-content imaging (CellInsight CX7) was used to extract mean speck intensity per cell (ASC-GFP assay) or percentage of PI-positive cells (pyroptosis assay), along with quantitative readouts of total cell count and nuclear intensity as integrated cellular health measures.

Treatment with LPS (10 ng/mL) for 22 hours induced ASC-GFP expression in the THP-1/ASC-GFP cells, and subsequent exposure to nigericin (10 μ M, 90 min) resulted in ASC-GFP specks indicative of inflammasome formation, typically with one inflammasome per cell, whereas negative control cells displayed no or weak/diffuse ASC-GFP signals in the cytosol (**Figure 7A**). For each 384-well plate, two columns (32 wells) each were allocated to negative and positive controls, which were used to monitor assay quality, with a Z' factor >0.4 as the acceptance criterion. In parallel, we established a pyroptosis assay using wild-type THP-1 cells under the identical 384-well assay conditions, detecting cell death via dual staining with Hoechst 33342 (cell membrane permeable, labeling all cells) and propidium iodide (membrane impermeable, labeling only dead cells), which allowed quantification of total cell counts, dead cell counts, and percentage cell death in each well. Using the paired assays, we tested the known NLRP3 inhibitor MCC950 across a 10-point concentration range and observed clear inhibition of inflammasome formation (**Figure 7A**) along with dose-dependent inhibition of pyroptosis (**Figure 7B**), with submicromolar potency. Taking advantage of the multiplex detection capability of high-content imaging assays, we also collected total cell counts and average nuclear intensity signals from each well to monitor cell health, which enabled the identification of treatment-induced cytotoxicity.

A. Inflammasome assay

B. Pyroptosis assay

Figure 7. Establishment of quantitative 384-well assays for the inflammasome pathway. (A) Inflammasome assay with THP-1/ASC-GFP cells. Example images show negative control wells with no or very few ASC-GFP specks and positive wells treated with LPS (priming) followed by nigericin (induction), which displayed ASC-GFP specks in most cells. The signal difference between negative and positive controls yielded a Z' factor of 0.67, and responses to serial dilutions of MCC950 enabled potency determination in this assay. **(B)** Pyroptosis assay with wild-type THP-1 cells. Example images show negative control wells with no or very few PI-stained dead cells and positive wells treated with LPS (priming) followed by nigericin (induction), in which >70% of cells were dead. The signal difference between negative and positive controls yielded a Z' factor of 0.78, and responses to serial dilutions of MCC950 enabled potency determination in this assay. In addition, the assay collected total cell counts and average nuclear intensity to monitor cell health, and overlaying the curves for these two measurements showed no change following MCC950 treatment.

With the assays successfully established, we evaluated the remaining literature-selected compounds using the optimized inflammasome and pyroptosis assays, performed in parallel to ensure identical compound preparations and serial dilutions for both readouts. As shown in **Table 1**, these compounds displayed a broad potency range from sub-nanomolar to inactive (>20 μM) in both assays. For MCC950, the measured inflammasome and pyroptosis IC_{50} values (437 and 542 nM, respectively) (**Figure 8A**) were higher than the reported IL-1 β production IC_{50} value of 29 nM. Inzomelid similarly exhibited reduced activity, with IC_{50} values of 5.8 and 39.5 μM , over 100-fold less potent than the reported IL-1 β production inhibition (<100 nM).

Table 1. Inflammasome and pyroptosis IC₅₀ values of the tested compounds

Compound	Inflammasome IC ₅₀ (nM) (mean ± SD, (n))	Pyroptosis IC ₅₀ (nM) (mean ± SD, (n))
MCC950	437.1 ± 89.8 (12)	542.8 ± 105.8 (12)
Inzomelid (MCC784)	5880 ± 472 (8)	9522 ± 2704 (8),
6a (TAD-0422360)	0.757 ± 0.212 (8)	0.795 ± 0.142 (8)
6b (TAD-0422361)	53 ± 11.8 (8)	82 ± 11.6 (8)
6c (TAD-0422357)	1.418 ± 0.29 (8)	1.291 ± 0.213 (8)
6d (TAD-0422364)	209.5 ± 61.9 (8)	208.3 ± 53.3 (8)
7a (TAD-0422256)	>20000 (4)	>20000 (4)
7b (TAD-0422255)	>20000 (4)	>20000 (4)
7c (TAD-0422242)	6373 ± 512 (6)	6364 ± 1958 (6)
7d (TAD-0422265)	6382 ± 1159 (6)	13882 ± 5280 (6)
7e (TAD-0422302)	>20000 (4)	>20000 (4)
7f (TAD-0422303)	4766 ± 2104 (4)	9120 ± 1697 (4)
8 (TAD-0422345)	0.582 ± 0.159 (8)	0.834 ± 0.226 (8)
9 (TAD-0422337)	5462.7 ± 1573 (6)	11106.4 ± 4628 (6)

IC₅₀ values represent the concentration of compound required to inhibit 50% of inflammasome activation or pyroptosis, determined from dose–response curves in THP-1 ASC-GFP cells. Values are expressed as mean ± SD, with *n* indicating the number of biological replicates. “>20 000 nM” denotes no measurable inhibition within the tested concentration range. MCC950 and Inzomelid (MCC784) were included as reference NLRP3 inhibitors. Compounds highlighted in blue (**6a** and **8**) represent the two compounds selected from reference 18.

Compounds **6a** and **6b**, cis isomers analogous to example 72A, displayed pyroptosis IC₅₀ values of 0.79 and 82 nM, respectively, with the former closely matching the reported value of 1.0 nM (*3aS,7aR* absolute stereochemistry) and the latter consistent with the reduced potency of the *3aR,7aS* isomer (example 72B, IC₅₀ = 309 nM). These results support assignment of the absolute stereochemistry of **6a** and **6b** as *3aS,7aR* and *3aR,7aS*, respectively, with corresponding pyroptosis IC₅₀ values of similar magnitude. The inflammasome inhibition potency values (IC₅₀) of these compounds were also of similar magnitude to their pyroptosis potency (**Table 1**). The racemate of the cis isomer (**6c**) also showed potent activity in both assays (inflammasome IC₅₀ = 1.418 nM and pyroptosis IC₅₀ = 1.291 nM), while the racemate of the trans isomer (**6d**) retained moderate potency (inflammasome IC₅₀ = 209.5 nM and pyroptosis IC₅₀ = 208.3 nM), indicating one highly active enantiomer. Compound **8**, corresponding to example 45, exhibited a pyroptosis potency (IC₅₀ = 0.834 nM) in close agreement with the reported 0.9 nM value, further highlighting correspondence between the assay (**Figure 8B**). None of the phoxymethyl derivatives (**7a-f** and **9**) were active in either assay, underscoring the importance of the phenol functionality for inflammasome inhibition and highlighting the capability of these assays to capture structure-activity relationships (SAR). In addition, the paired assays correlated strongly (R = 0.94), confirming that both

measurements closely related inflammasome pathway events despite using THP1 cells from different origins.

Figure 8. Examples of dose-response curves and assay correlation. (A) Dose-response curves for inflammasome and pyroptosis assays for MCC950 (left) and inzomelid (right). (B) Dose-response curves for inflammasome and pyroptosis assays for compounds 8 (left) and 9 (right). Note that methylation resulted in a loss of activity in both assays, which is clearly captured.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we established and optimized paired high-content imaging assays that quantitatively measure ASC speck formation and pyroptosis, enabling direct and comparative assessment of NLRP3 inflammasome inhibitors. Using these assays, we evaluated a structurally diverse set of compounds selected for both potency and CNS drug-like properties, including MCC950, inzomelid, and two compounds with distinct chemotypes selected from a recently published patent application. Our results revealed a high correlation between inflammasome and pyroptosis inhibitory activities, supporting the utility of either assay for initial screening, with pyroptosis serving as the preferred format for follow-up studies. We confirmed the critical role of the phenol functionality in the fused bicyclic heteroaryl chemotype (Compounds **6a-d**, **7a-f**, **8**, and **9**) for NLRP3 inhibition, demonstrated that the absolute stereochemistry of these compounds strongly influences potency, and identified previously unreported racemic analogs with nanomolar activity. The high reproducibility of our results with literature values, particularly for compounds evaluated in the same cellular background, validates the accuracy and translational relevance of our assay platform. As a service to the community, all compounds described in this work will be made available as 50 μ L aliquots of 10 mM solutions.

5. METHODS

5.1 General Procedures

MCC950 (Cat. No. HY-12815) and Inzomelid (Cat. No. HY-137245) were purchased from MedChemExpress and used as received in the experiments. Compounds **6a-d**, **7a-f**, **8**, and **9** were synthesized according to the published protocol in reference 18 and subjected to chiral separation when applicable. The absolute stereochemistry of the separated enantiomers was not assigned, and they were used as received. The purities of the final compounds were greater than 95%, as determined by reverse-phase HPLC analysis.

5.2 Assay Protocol

Inflammasome assay with THP1/ASCGFP cells (Invivogen, Cat. No. thp-ascgfp): This high-content analysis assay was optimized in a 384-well plate format. Cells were cultured and tested in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated FBS and 1% penicillin-streptomycin (Millipore Sigma, P4333). The assay measures inflammasome formation for compounds tested in a 10-point, 3-fold serial dilution dose-response format. On Day 1, cells were plated into 384-well plates (10 000 cells/45 μ L/well), then cultured overnight at 37 °C, 5% CO₂ incubator. On Day 2, compound treatment was initiated 60 min before adding LPS (10 ng/mL) for 22 h at 37 °C (final DMSO concentration < 0.1%). On Day 3, cells were treated with 10 μ M nigericin for 90 min at 37 °C followed by staining with Hoechst 33342 (2 μ g/mL) for 30 min before imaging. High-content imaging was performed with the CellInsight CX7 automated imaging system (Thermo Scientific) and images analyzed using the system's software. Three measurements were extracted: **(1)** inflammasome signal, expressed as the mean total spot intensity per cell (primary output); **(2)** total cell counts per well to monitor cell health; and **(3)** mean nuclear intensity per cell as an additional cell health parameter. Dose-response curve analyses were performed using the GraphPad Prism software package (version 10.1.2).

THP1 pyroptosis assay with THP1 cells (ATCC, Cat. No. TIB-202): This high-content analysis assay was conducted in a 384-well plate format. Cells were cultured and tested in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented

with 10% heat-inactivated FBS and the 1% penicillin-streptomycin. The assay measures pyroptosis for compounds tested in a 10-point, 3-fold serial dilution dose-response format. On Day 1, cells were plated into 384-well plates (10,000 cells/45 μ L/well), then cultured overnight at 37 °C. On Day 2, compound treatment was initiated 60 min before adding LPS (10 ng/mL) for 22 h at 37 °C incubation (final DMSO concentration < 0.1%). On Day 3, cells were treated with 10 μ M nigericin for 90 min at 37 °C, followed by staining with Hoechst 33342 and propidium iodide (2 μ g/mL each) for 30 min before imaging. High-content imaging was performed with the CellInsight CX7 automated imaging system (Thermo Scientific), and images were analyzed using the system's software. Three measurements were extracted: **(1)** percentage of dead cells (primary output); **(2)** total cell counts per well to monitor cell health; and **(3)** mean nuclear intensity per cell as an additional cell health parameter. Dose-response curve analyses were performed using the GraphPad Prism software package (version 10.1.2).

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Kun Huang, Andrew D. Mesecar, Jeffrey L. Dage, Brent Clayton, Timothy I. Richardson, Bruce T. Lamb, and Alan Palkowitz are founders and consultants for Monument Biosciences. No other authors have conflict of interests to disclose.

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KEY WORDS

NLRP3, Inflammasome, MCC950, NACHT, Pyroptosis

DATA AVAILABILITY

Datasets will be made available via the AD Knowledge Portal.

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